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Male Fertility Preferences and Their Implications for Child and Adolescent Mental Health in Nigeria, Uganda, and South Africa: A Cross-Sectional Analysis of DHS Data

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Abstract

Introduction: Male fertility preferences significantly influence reproductive outcomes and family wellbeing in sub-Saharan Africa, yet their implications for child and adolescent mental health remain underexplored. This study examines the determinants of male fertility preferences and their potential developmental impacts in Nigeria, Uganda, and South Africa.

Methods: We analyzed harmonized data from the IPUMS-DHS men's files, including 20,825 male respondents across the three countries. The outcome variable (ideal number of children) was categorized as 1–3, 4–5, and 6 or more children. Multinomial logistic regression was used to assess associations with predictors at $p < 0.05$.

Results: Fertility preferences were highest in Nigeria (mean = 7.5), followed by Uganda (5.5) and South Africa (3.2). Men without formal education were nearly three times more likely to prefer six or more children than those with higher education (OR = 2.87; 95% CI: 2.32–3.54). Those in the poorest wealth quintile had over four times higher odds of desiring large families (OR = 4.55; 95% CI: 3.80–5.45). Justifying wife beating, rural residence, and low family planning media exposure were also significantly linked to higher fertility preferences.

Conclusions: High fertility aspirations among men, shaped by socioeconomic disadvantage and patriarchal norms, strain family resources and adversely affect child and adolescent mental health. Male-inclusive, gender-transformative reproductive health interventions are urgently needed to inform national policies and support the achievement of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) 3, 4, and 5.

Keywords: Adolescent Wellbeing; Child Mental Health; Family Planning; Gender Norms; Male Fertility Preference.

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INTRODUCTION

The role of men in shaping reproductive decisions and family dynamics remains a critical yet underexplored dimension of demographic and public health research in sub-Saharan Africa (SSA). Fertility preferences, particularly the number of children a man ideally desires, are not merely personal or cultural expressions but also reflect broader social norms, gender ideologies, and economic realities that directly influence family size, parenting structures, and the overall wellbeing of children [1–3]. Despite substantial literature focusing on women’s fertility behaviours, male preferences remain under-investigated, even though men continue to wield disproportionate influence in reproductive decision-making, contraceptive uptake, and family planning (FP) negotiations [4,5].

In many SSA societies, the preference for large families is driven by patriarchal norms, religious expectations, polygynous traditions, and the perceived economic value of children [6–8]. However, a mismatch often exists between these fertility aspirations and the actual economic or psychosocial capacity to support large families. This dissonance contributes to household stress, reduced investments per child, and adverse parenting practices that increase the risk of emotional, behavioural, and developmental disorders among children and adolescents [9–11].

Moreover, complex family arrangements, including multiple maternal births, absent fathers, or violent domestic contexts, exacerbate childhood vulnerability, especially when driven by unchecked male fertility behaviours [12–14]. Studies show that justification of wife beating (a proxy for patriarchal control) is associated with hostile home environments, which compromise children’s mental health and social development [15,16]. Male fertility preferences are further shaped by education, age, employment, access to mass media, and exposure to FP information [17–19]. These same factors also influence whether men actively support or undermine efforts to space or limit childbirth.

Importantly, the implications of male fertility preferences extend beyond reproductive health. They shape household stability, children’s access to care, and adolescent resilience in the face of psychosocial stressors. For example, fragmented families resulting from multiple partner fertility, a practice more common among men with higher fertility intentions, have been linked to increased mental distress among youth [20,21]. Yet, despite these critical linkages, there is limited cross-national evidence connecting male fertility preferences with household-level risk factors for child and adolescent mental health in SSA.

This study seeks to fill this gap by exploring both the determinants of male fertility preferences and their associations with indicators relevant to child and adolescent mental health in three socio-culturally distinct SSA countries (Nigeria, Uganda, and South Africa). These countries provide contrasting demographic and policy contexts: Nigeria has one of the highest fertility rates globally, Uganda exhibits a youthful population structure with growing gender-responsive policy efforts, while South Africa presents a relatively advanced fertility transition with strong legal frameworks on gender and health [22–24].

Using harmonized and nationally representative data from the IPUMS-Demographic and Health Surveys (DHS), this study addresses two core questions: (1) What demographic, socioeconomic, and ideational factors are associated with male fertility preferences in these countries? (2) How are male fertility preferences associated with household

conditions that influence child and adolescent mental health such as number of children fathered, justification of intimate partner violence, and male reproductive behaviour (e.g., number of partners with children)?

By investigating these interlinked dynamics, the study contributes to a more nuanced understanding of how men's reproductive ideologies shape not just population outcomes but also the emotional and developmental trajectories of the next generation. Findings can inform policies that integrate reproductive health and mental health programming and demonstrate the importance of engaging men in both FP and child wellbeing initiatives [25–27].

METHODS

Study Design and Data Source

This was a cross-sectional analytical study based on secondary data from the IPUMS-Demographic and Health Surveys (IPUMS-DHS) men's recode files [28]. The study utilized harmonized data from three SSA countries - Nigeria (2018), Uganda (2016), and South Africa (2016); selected for their diverse fertility patterns, sociocultural contexts, and policy environments. IPUMS-DHS provides publicly available, de-identified survey datasets harmonized across countries and time to facilitate comparative research.

Study Population and Sample Size

The target population comprised male respondents aged 15–59 years who were included in the men's module of the DHS in the respective countries. After data cleaning and the application of relevant sample weights, the final analytic sample included 20,825 men with complete data on the variables of interest.

Outcome Variable

The primary outcome variable was male fertility preference, operationalized using the DHS question on “ideal number of children”. For analysis, responses were recoded into three categories: 1–3 children (coded 1), 4–5 children (coded 2) and 6 or more children (coded 3). Responses of “don't know” or missing values were excluded.

Explanatory Variables

Ten key independent variables were selected based on theoretical relevance and prior literature:

1. Age group (15–29, 30–39, 40–49, 50–59)
2. Highest educational level (No education, Primary, Secondary, Tertiary)
3. Household wealth index (Poorest to Richest quintiles)
4. Current working status (Yes/No)
5. Exposure to FP messages in media (Yes/No)
6. Urban–rural residence (Urban/Rural)
7. Country of residence (Nigeria, Uganda, South Africa)
8. Number of women fathered children With (0, 1, 2 or more)
9. Justification of wife beating (Any justification vs. none)
10. Number of living biological children (None, 1–3, 4 or more)

These variables were either already harmonized in IPUMS-DHS or recoded as required to ensure consistency across the three countries.

Statistical Analysis

All analyses were conducted using IBM SPSS Statistics version 30 and were weighted using the men's sample weights to account for complex survey design and ensure national representativeness. Descriptive statistics were presented as weighted percentages and frequencies. Bivariate analysis used chi-square tests to assess associations between the outcome and each explanatory variable. Multivariable analysis employed multinomial logistic regression to identify independent predictors of male fertility preferences. The model estimated the odds of preferring 4–5 or 6+

children relative to 1–3 children (the reference category). Adjusted odds ratios (AOR) with 95% confidence intervals (CI) were reported. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$. The regression model controlled for potential multicollinearity and confounding. Severe multicollinearity was not indicated as variable impact factor (VIF) values were below 2. Variables were retained based on theoretical justification, statistical significance, and relevance to the research question. This study was designed and reported in line with the STROBE guidelines for cross-sectional studies[29].

Ethical Aspects

This research involved a secondary analysis of de-identified, publicly available data obtained from the DHS Program via the IPUMS-DHS platform. The original data collection was conducted by ICF International in collaboration with national ethical review boards in each participating country, with ethical approval secured (ICF IRB FWA00000845). Written informed consent was obtained from all respondents, and the surveys adhered to the ethical principles outlined in the Declaration of Helsinki. As the data are publicly accessible to registered users at: <https://www.idhsdata.org/idhs/>. No further ethical approval was necessary for this secondary analysis.

RESULTS

Table 1 presents the background characteristics of male respondents across Nigeria, South Africa, and Uganda using harmonized IPUMS-DHS data. The majority of respondents were aged 15–29 years, with Uganda having the highest proportion in this age group (56.4%), followed by South Africa (48.3%) and Nigeria (40.8%). Conversely, Nigeria had the highest proportion of respondents aged 40 years and above (31.5%), indicating an older male demographic compared to Uganda and South Africa. Educational attainment varied across countries. While secondary education was the most common level attained in all three countries, South Africa had a notably higher proportion of men with secondary education (72.2%) compared to Nigeria (46.4%) and Uganda (28.5%). Uganda had the highest proportion of men with only primary education (54.8%), whereas Nigeria had the largest share of men with no formal education (21.4%). Regarding household wealth, all three countries exhibited fairly even distributions across the quintiles. However, South Africa had the highest proportion of men in the poorest and poorer wealth quintiles combined (40.1%), whereas Nigeria had the largest share in the richest quintile (24.2%).

Employment status showed notable variation. Over 92% of men in Uganda and 87.6% in Nigeria were currently working, compared to only 47.2% in South Africa. In contrast, more than half of South African men were not currently working (52.8%). Exposure to FP messages through media was highest in Uganda (74.5%), moderate in South Africa (52.8%), and lowest in Nigeria (46.2%). Justification of wife beating was most common in Uganda (40.4%) and least common in South Africa (8.8%). Regarding fertility characteristics, 41.7% of all male respondents reported having no living biological children. Uganda had the highest proportion of men with four or more children (32.0%), while South Africa had the lowest (12.0%). Similarly, 23.8% of Ugandan men reported fathering children with two or more women, compared to 13.3% in Nigeria and 18.9% in South Africa. Rural residence was most prevalent in Uganda (75.0%) and Nigeria (53.0%), while the majority of South African respondents lived in urban areas (68.8%). These differences reflect the demographic, socio-economic, and cultural diversity across the three countries and provide a valuable context for interpreting male fertility preferences and related implications for child and adolescent mental health.

Table 1. Background characteristics of male respondents by country.

Characteristic	Nigeria n (%)	South Africa n (%)	Uganda n (%)	Total n (%)
<i>Age Group</i>				
15–29	5010 (40.8%)	1684 (48.3%)	2878 (56.4%)	9572 (45.8%)

30–39	3413 (27.8%)	820 (23.5%)	1182 (23.2%)	5415 (25.9%)
40–49	2547 (20.7%)	595 (17.1%)	767 (15.0%)	3909 (18.7%)
50–59	1323 (10.8%)	387 (11.1%)	274 (5.4%)	1984 (9.5%)
<i>Educational Level</i>				
None	2636 (21.4%)	97 (2.8%)	207 (4.1%)	2940 (14.1%)
Primary	1765 (14.4%)	485 (13.9%)	2795 (54.8%)	5045 (24.2%)
Secondary	5700 (46.4%)	2516 (72.2%)	1456 (28.5%)	9672 (46.3%)
Higher	2191 (17.8%)	388 (11.1%)	642 (12.6%)	3221 (15.4%)
<i>Wealth Quintile</i>				
Poorest	1950 (15.9%)	681 (19.5%)	858 (16.8%)	3489 (16.7%)
Poorer	2229 (18.1%)	719 (20.6%)	904 (17.7%)	3852 (18.4%)
Middle	2471 (20.1%)	744 (21.3%)	1001 (19.6%)	4216 (20.2%)
Richer	2663 (21.7%)	721 (20.7%)	1121 (22.0%)	4505 (21.6%)
Richest	2980 (24.2%)	622 (17.8%)	1217 (23.9%)	4819 (23.1%)
<i>Currently Working</i>				
Yes	10770 (87.6%)	1646 (47.2%)	4721 (92.6%)	17137 (82.1%)
No	1523 (12.4%)	1840 (52.8%)	380 (7.4%)	3743 (17.9%)
<i>Exposed to FP Message in Media</i>				
Yes	5681 (46.2%)	1840 (52.8%)	3803 (74.5%)	11324 (54.2%)
No	6611 (53.8%)	1646 (47.2%)	1299 (25.5%)	9556 (45.8%)
<i>Justifies Wife Beating</i>				
Yes	2511 (20.4%)	308 (8.8%)	2060 (40.4%)	4879 (23.4%)
No	9781 (79.6%)	3178 (91.2%)	3041 (59.6%)	16000 (76.6%)
<i>Living Children</i>				
None	4955 (40.3%)	1630 (46.8%)	2130 (41.7%)	8715 (41.7%)
1–3	3690 (30.0%)	1438 (41.3%)	1339 (26.2%)	6467 (31.0%)
4 or more	3648 (29.7%)	418 (12.0%)	1633 (32.0%)	5699 (27.3%)
<i>Women Fathered Children With</i>				
0	4873 (39.6%)	1600 (45.9%)	2097 (41.1%)	8570 (41.0%)
1	5790 (47.1%)	1228 (35.2%)	1791 (35.1%)	8809 (42.2%)
2 or more	1630 (13.3%)	658 (18.9%)	1214 (23.8%)	3502 (16.8%)
<i>Residence</i>				
Urban	5777 (47.0%)	2400 (68.8%)	1275 (25.0%)	9452 (45.3%)
Rural	6515 (53.0%)	1086 (31.2%)	3827 (75.0%)	11428 (54.7%)

Note: n = frequency; % = percentage

Figure 1 illustrates the average ideal number of children as reported by male respondents across Nigeria, Uganda, and South Africa. The data show notable cross-country differences. Nigeria has the highest fertility preference, with men reporting an average of 7.5 children. Ugandan men report a lower preference, averaging 5.5 children. South African men show the lowest fertility preference, with a mean of 3.2 children. These differences likely reflect underlying variations in socio-cultural norms, economic development, access to FP services, and national reproductive health policies.

The markedly higher preference in Nigeria may signal continued pronatalist values and limited male engagement in FP, with implications for population growth and household-level resource allocation as further interrogated in the follow up advanced analysis.

Figure 1. Ideal number of children (male respondents) by country.

Table 2 presents the bivariate associations between selected sociodemographic characteristics and male fertility preferences (measured as the ideal number of children grouped into 1–3, 4–5, and 6 or more children) across Nigeria, Uganda, and South Africa. All associations were statistically significant at $p < 0.001$. Age was significantly associated with fertility preferences. Younger men aged 15–29 years were more likely to prefer 1–3 children (26.0%) compared to older men. The proportion of men preferring six or more children increased steadily with age, reaching 52.9% among those aged 50–59 years. Educational attainment showed a strong inverse relationship with fertility preferences. Men with no education had the highest preference for six or more children (79.0%), while those with higher education had the lowest (29.2%). Conversely, preference for 1–3 children was highest among men with secondary (27.8%) and higher (27.9%) education. Household wealth was also significantly associated with fertility preferences. Men in the poorest quintile were more likely to prefer larger families (57.5% preferred six or more children), whereas those in the richest quintile showed a stronger preference for smaller families, with 29.5% desiring 1–3 children. Employment status influenced fertility ideals, with currently working men more likely to prefer six or more children (44.3%) compared to unemployed men (21.4%), who leaned more toward having 1–3 children (43.7%). Exposure to FP (FP) messages had a moderating effect. Men exposed to FP messages in the media were more likely to prefer 4–5 children (41.9%) and less likely to prefer six or more children (35.5%) compared to their unexposed counterparts (45.8% preferred six or more children).

Place of residence was associated with fertility preferences. Urban men more commonly preferred smaller families (30.1% for 1–3 children) than rural men (15.5%), whereas rural men exhibited a stronger inclination toward larger families (49.7% for six or more children). Country-level differences were significant. Nigerian men most frequently preferred six or more children (50.8%), followed by Ugandans (36.4%), while South African men had a much stronger preference for smaller families, with 62.7% selecting 1–3 children and only 8.7% preferring six or more. Number of

women fathered children with also influenced preferences. Among men with children by two or more women, 61.0% preferred six or more children, compared to 31.5% among those who had not fathered children or only with one woman. Attitudes toward wife beating were linked to higher fertility preferences. Men who justified wife beating were more likely to prefer larger families (49.7% for six or more children) compared to those who rejected such justification (37.4%). Number of living children was a strong predictor. Men with four or more living children overwhelmingly preferred six or more children (66.2%), while those with none or few living children expressed preferences for smaller family sizes. Overall, the bivariate analysis demonstrates that socio-economic status, exposure to media, place of residence, and cultural attitudes significantly shape men's fertility preferences, with potential implications for family size, child-rearing practices, and subsequent child and adolescent mental health.

Table 2. Bivariate associations between male fertility preference groups and selected characteristics (N = 20,880).

Variable / Category	Total (n)	1–3 Children (%)	4–5 Children (%)	6 or More Children (%)	χ^2	p-value
<i>Age Group</i>					461.49	<0.001
15–29	9,572	26.0%	40.3%	33.7%		
30–39	5,415	20.6%	38.5%	40.8%		
40–49	3,910	17.0%	34.0%	49.0%		
50–59	1,983	17.2%	29.9%	52.9%		
<i>Educational Level</i>					2550.65	<0.001
No Education	2,939	6.7%	14.3%	79.0%		
Primary	5,046	16.3%	39.5%	44.2%		
Secondary	9,673	27.8%	42.1%	30.1%		
Higher	3,222	27.9%	42.8%	29.2%		
<i>Wealth Quintile</i>					1482.07	<0.001
Poorest	3,489	16.5%	26.0%	57.5%		
Poorer	3,852	17.7%	30.5%	51.8%		
Middle	4,215	19.9%	35.6%	44.6%		
Richer	4,505	24.3%	42.7%	33.0%		
Richest	4,819	29.5%	49.0%	21.5%		
<i>Currently Working</i>					1379.16	<0.001
No	3,743	43.7%	34.9%	21.4%		
Yes	17,137	17.4%	38.3%	44.3%		
<i>FP Message Exposure (Media)</i>					255.13	<0.001
No	9,557	21.5%	32.7%	45.8%		
Yes	11,323	22.6%	41.9%	35.5%		
<i>Urban-Rural Status</i>					1115.70	<0.001
Urban	9,452	30.1%	41.1%	28.8%		
Rural	11,427	15.5%	34.8%	49.7%		
<i>Country</i>					4574.38	<0.001
Nigeria	12,292	12.9%	36.3%	50.8%		
Uganda	5,101	16.5%	47.1%	36.4%		

South Africa	3,487	62.7%	28.6%	8.7%		
<i>No. of Women Fathered Children With</i>					1063.25	<0.001
0	8,570	29.2%	39.3%	31.5%		
1	8,809	18.8%	40.6%	40.5%		
2+	3,502	12.7%	26.3%	61.0%		
<i>Justifies Wife Beating (Any Reason)</i>					326.05	<0.001
No	16,000	24.5%	38.1%	37.4%		
Yes	4,880	14.2%	36.2%	49.7%		
<i>No. of Living Children (Grouped)</i>					2404.90	<0.001
None	8,714	29.2%	39.3%	31.5%		
1–3	6,467	25.6%	45.2%	29.2%		
4+	5,699	7.3%	26.6%	66.2%		

Note: *n* = frequency; % = percentage

Table 3 presents the results of the multinomial logistic regression examining the predictors of men's fertility preferences categorized as 1–3 (reference group), 4–5, and 6 or more children across Nigeria, Uganda, and South Africa. Age group was significantly associated with fertility preferences. Compared to men aged 50–59 (reference), those aged 15–29 were 1.29 times more likely to prefer 4–5 children (AOR = 1.29; 95% CI: 1.06–1.57; $p < 0.01$) and 1.77 times more likely to prefer 6 or more children (AOR = 1.77; 95% CI: 1.43–2.19; $p < 0.001$). The 30–39 age group also showed higher odds for preferring 6 or more children (AOR = 1.26; $p < 0.05$), while the 40–49 group showed no statistically significant difference. Education level showed a consistent and inverse relationship with fertility preference. Men with no formal education were nearly three times more likely to prefer six or more children than those with higher education (AOR = 2.87; 95% CI: 2.32–3.54; $p < 0.001$). Those with only primary (AOR = 1.33) and secondary education (AOR = 1.15) also had increased odds compared to those with tertiary education. Household wealth index had a strong negative gradient effect.

Compared to men in the richest quintile, those in the poorest quintile were 4.55 times more likely to prefer six or more children (AOR = 4.55; $p < 0.001$), with progressively decreasing odds as wealth increased. Men not currently working were significantly less likely to prefer larger families (AOR = 0.76 for 6+ children; $p < 0.001$). Exposure to FP messages in the media had a protective effect for preferring moderate fertility (4–5 children), as unexposed men were slightly less likely to prefer 4–5 children (AOR = 0.89; $p < 0.05$). The effect on high fertility (6 or more) was not statistically significant. Urban residence was associated with a lower likelihood of preferring high fertility. Urban men were significantly less likely to prefer six or more children than rural men (AOR = 0.85; $p = 0.002$).

Country differences were pronounced. Nigerian men were 6.80 times more likely to prefer 4–5 children and over 30 times more likely to prefer 6+ children compared to South Africans ($p < 0.001$). Ugandan men also showed increased odds (AOR = 5.47 for 4–5; AOR = 11.23 for 6+). Men who had fathered children with only one woman (AOR = 0.44) or none (AOR = 0.43) were significantly less likely to prefer large families compared to those with two or more partners. Justifying wife beating was associated with higher fertility preference. Men who rejected wife beating were significantly less likely to prefer 6 or more children (AOR = 0.63; $p < 0.001$). Men with fewer living children were less likely to express a preference for larger family sizes. Those with no living children had an 88% lower likelihood of preferring 6+ children (AOR = 0.12; $p < 0.001$), and those with 1–3 children were similarly less likely (AOR = 0.18; $p < 0.001$).

Table 3. Multinomial logistic regression predicting ideal number of children among men in Nigeria, Uganda, and South Africa.

Predictor	aOR for 4–5 (vs. 1–3)	95% CI	aOR for 6+ (vs. 1–3)	95% CI
<i>Age Group (Ref: 55+)</i>				
15–24	1.29**	[1.06, 1.57]	1.77***	[1.43, 2.19]
25–34	1.07	[0.90, 1.28]	1.26*	[1.04, 1.53]
35–44	1.03	[0.86, 1.24]	1.11	[0.91, 1.34]
45–54	Ref	–	Ref	–
<i>Education (Ref: Higher)</i>				
No education	0.96	[0.78, 1.19]	2.87***	[2.32, 3.54]
Primary	1.32***	[1.14, 1.52]	1.33***	[1.14, 1.56]
Secondary	1.39***	[1.24, 1.56]	1.15*	[1.01, 1.31]
<i>Wealth Quintile (Ref: Richest)</i>				
Poorest	1.51***	[1.29, 1.78]	4.55***	[3.80, 5.45]
Poorer	1.39***	[1.20, 1.61]	3.84***	[3.26, 4.52]
Middle	1.32***	[1.16, 1.51]	3.16***	[2.73, 3.66]
Richer	1.15*	[1.03, 1.29]	1.83***	[1.61, 2.09]
<i>Currently Working (Ref: Yes)</i>				
No	0.82***	[0.74, 0.92]	0.76***	[0.67, 0.86]
<i>FP Media Exposure (Ref: Yes)</i>				
No	0.89*	[0.82, 0.97]	1.07	[0.97, 1.17]
<i>Residence (Ref: Rural)</i>				
Urban	0.90*	[0.82, 1.00]	0.85**	[0.76, 0.94]
<i>Country (Ref: South Africa)</i>				
Nigeria	6.80***	[6.07, 7.61]	30.09***	[25.61, 35.36]
Uganda	5.47***	[4.73, 6.31]	11.23***	[9.30, 13.56]
<i>Fathered children with (Ref: 2+ women)</i>				
0 women	0.59*	[0.37, 0.96]	0.43**	[0.25, 0.75]
1 woman	0.84*	[0.72, 0.97]	0.44***	[0.37, 0.51]
<i>Justifies Wife Beating (Ref: Yes)</i>				
No	0.85**	[0.76, 0.94]	0.63***	[0.56, 0.70]
<i>No. of Living Children (Ref: 4+)</i>				
None	0.51**	[0.32, 0.82]	0.12***	[0.07, 0.21]
1–3	0.60***	[0.52, 0.69]	0.18***	[0.16, 0.21]

Note: *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, ***p < 0.001; aOR = Adjusted Odds Ratio; CI = Confidence Interval; Ref = Reference categories noted in parentheses.

DISCUSSION

This study investigated the determinants of male fertility preferences in Nigeria, Uganda, and South Africa using harmonized IPUMS-DHS data. Findings show that men's fertility preferences are shaped by interplay of demographic, socioeconomic, ideational, and contextual factors, with critical implications for child and adolescent mental health. The discussion situates findings within the broader literature and highlights areas of convergence and divergence with

existing research across Africa and other LMICs. This study found that younger men (15–29 years) had significantly higher odds of fertility preferences. This is consistent with findings from Ethiopia [30] and Nigeria [31], where younger males associated high fertility with masculinity, virility, and social recognition. However, this contrasts with studies in Ghana [18], which found a decline in large fertility aspirations among educated urban youth, indicating a generational shift in reproductive norms. Our results suggest that younger men, while aspirational, may not consider the psychosocial burden of higher fertility preference or large family size on children, including reduced parental attention and emotional availability [9].

A clear inverse relationship was observed between male education and preference for high fertility, affirming findings from Uganda [32] and Zambia [33]. Educated men are more likely to be exposed to modern FP messaging and better understand the emotional and developmental needs of children. Our results align with an earlier study that higher education among Ugandan men significantly lowered their fertility intentions [34]. This consensus emphasizes the role of education in promoting child-centred and mental health-aware reproductive behaviour. Men in the lowest wealth quintiles were more likely to prefer larger families, supporting findings from Mozambique [15], where economic instability drives pronatalist values, as children are perceived as economic assets. However, this differs from recent South African data [17], which suggest that economic insecurity increasingly prompts family size limitation due to rising child-rearing costs. These mixed patterns imply that context-specific economic and cultural values jointly influence fertility goals.

Consistent with studies in Nigeria and Uganda [1,35,36], urban residence and exposure to FP messages were associated with fewer fertility preferences. Urban environments tend to offer greater access to information, education, and social norms that emphasize child wellbeing, quality parenting, and mental health. A study in Ethiopia [37] similarly found that media exposure reduced the perceived burden of contraceptive side effects and improved men's openness to smaller families, reinforcing our findings. Men who opposed wife-beating and had children with fewer women were less likely to desire high fertility. This supports evidence from South Africa [12] and Ghana [13] that equitable gender attitudes and monogamous partnerships foster more stable family environments. These environments are crucial for promoting child mental health through consistent caregiving and reduced exposure to conflict. However, this diverges from results in Northern Nigeria [19], where polygyny and male dominance remain deeply rooted and continue to drive large fertility preferences, often to the detriment of child mental health.

The finding that Nigerian and Ugandan men are significantly more likely to prefer high fertility compared to South African men aligns with global report on the three countries' national fertility data [22]. Nigeria and Uganda, high fertility norms persist due to weak reproductive health policies and strong pronatalist traditions. Conversely, South Africa's relatively advanced fertility transition, gender policies, and reproductive rights framework likely contribute to lower fertility preferences and more supportive environments for child development and mental health [24,38]. Men with four or more living children still expressed a desire for more, echoing findings from Kebbi State, Nigeria [31] and Northern Uganda [21], where social pressure to continue childbearing, often to produce male heirs or fulfill clan expectations, remains strong. However, this contradicts research reported in Ethiopia [39], where high parity was associated with lower subsequent fertility preferences, attributed to awareness of parenting burden and economic limits. This disagreement may reflect differences in policy exposure, cultural orientation, or access to mental health and parenting education services.

The mental health risks for children in large, unstable families, with high fertility preferences, highlighted in this study, echo an argument from the recent study in Ethiopia, which stressed how family economic stress, violence, and neglect contribute to poor mental health trajectories [11]. Similarly, the work in Ugandan refugee settlements shows that

household instability and lack of parental support are major predictors of PTSD and depression in children [16]. This emphasizes that child mental health interventions must incorporate reproductive education and promote male engagement in caregiving and child welfare.

Implications for Policy, Child and Adolescent Mental Health

The implications of these findings for child and adolescent mental health are profound. Male fertility preferences shape FP decisions, which in turn determine the home environment in which children grow. Overly large families, especially in resource-poor settings, often struggle to provide the emotional, cognitive, and material support essential for healthy psychological development. Policymakers must integrate male-inclusive reproductive health strategies with child mental health interventions, emphasizing responsible fatherhood, optimal family size, and the developmental benefits of child spacing. In addition, media campaigns and educational programs should explicitly connect FP with child mental wellbeing, using culturally sensitive messaging to shift norms around masculinity and fertility. Mental health services, particularly for adolescents, should be tailored to account for the contextual realities of family size, household composition, and paternal involvement.

Furthermore, multi-sectoral collaboration is essential to ensure that reproductive health, education, and social welfare systems work synergistically to identify at-risk children and adolescents from large or unstable households. National policies should support integrated service delivery that include counselling for fathers, parent-child bonding programs, and targeted support for adolescents coping with the psychosocial burdens of overcrowded or fractured family environments. By aligning fertility preference interventions with mental health promotion, governments can make meaningful progress in improving the wellbeing and life outcomes of the next generation.

Strengths and Limitations

This study offers several notable strengths. First, it utilizes nationally representative and harmonized datasets from the IPUMS-DHS covering three diverse SSA countries - Nigeria, Uganda, and South Africa. This broadens the analytical scope and enhances the generalizability of the findings across different socio-cultural and policy contexts. Second, by focusing on men's fertility preferences and incorporating variables such as number of living children, justification of wife beating, and number of women fathered children with, the study provides a novel gendered lens on reproductive intentions and their potential implications for child and adolescent mental health. The inclusion of predictors related to family structure, exposure to FP messages, and justification of gender norms offers a multidimensional understanding of male fertility preferences. Additionally, the use of multinomial logistic regression allows for nuanced interpretation of how various socioeconomic and attitudinal factors are associated with different ideal family size categories, while also adjusting for potential confounders. This analytical approach offers robust statistical control and strengthens the credibility of the findings.

However, this study is not without limitations. The cross-sectional nature of the DHS data constrains the ability to draw causal inferences between the predictors and fertility preferences. Furthermore, the study relies on indirect proxies (e.g., number of living children, justification of wife beating, and fathering with multiple women) to infer potential implications for child and adolescent mental health, as the DHS does not directly measure mental health outcomes. This may limit the precision of such implications. In addition, social desirability bias could influence male responses on sensitive issues such as fertility intentions, gender norms, and number of partners. Lastly, cultural and contextual differences between countries may affect the comparability of findings despite harmonized variable coding.

CONCLUSIONS

This study provides important cross-country insights into the determinants of male fertility preferences in Nigeria, Uganda, and South Africa, with critical implications for child and adolescent mental health. By identifying how

education, wealth, media exposure, and gender norms shape men's desired family size, the findings offer a nuanced understanding of male reproductive agency; an often overlooked but essential component in achieving sustainable population and development outcomes. The study aligns closely with Sustainable Development Goal 3 (Good Health and Wellbeing), particularly Target 3.7, which advocates universal access to sexual and reproductive healthcare services, and with SDG 5 (Gender Equality), which calls for the elimination of harmful practices and greater shared responsibility in reproductive decision-making. It also supports SDG 4 (Quality Education) and SDG 10 (Reduced Inequalities), given the clear intersections between fertility preferences, socio-economic status, and family wellbeing. Nationally, the findings resonate with the goals of Nigeria's National Policy on Population for Sustainable Development, Uganda's National Adolescent Health Policy, and South Africa's National Development Plan (Vision 2030), which prioritize FP, youth empowerment, and mental health as pillars for national progress.

This research is both timely and critical. Across SSA, rapid population growth, unmet need for FP, and rising adolescent mental health concerns are converging to create a complex public health challenge. Male fertility preferences have remained a blind spot in many policy interventions, often leading to fragmented efforts in reproductive health that exclude a key actor (men). If the recommendations of this study are not urgently adopted and translated into actionable policies and programs, the consequences may be severe. Overburdened households will continue to face economic strain, increased child neglect, limited access to education and healthcare, and heightened risk of psychosocial stress for children and adolescents. These pressures can heighten cycles of poverty, gender inequality, and intergenerational trauma, undermining national development gains. Therefore, integrating male fertility perspectives into reproductive health policies and linking them explicitly with strategies to promote child and adolescent mental health is not just beneficial; it is essential. Only through inclusive, evidence-informed policy responses can we secure healthier families, more equitable societies, and resilient future generations in Africa.

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References

1. Mutumba M. Mass media influences on family planning knowledge, attitudes and method choice among sexually active men in sub-Saharan Africa. *PLoS One*. 2022 Jan 27;17(1):e0261068.
2. Okonofua F, Ntoimo LF, Ng'ambi W, Muula A, Ndiaye O, Ogaji D, et al. Male perceptions of family planning in four sub-Saharan African countries: Evidence from demographic and health surveys. *Heliyon*. 2025 May;11(10):e43418.
3. Church AC, Ibitoye M, Chettri S, Casterline JB. Traditional supports and contemporary disrupters of high fertility desires in sub-Saharan Africa: a scoping review. *Reprod Health*. 2023 Dec 1;20(1).
4. Afachung OA, Oluwasanu MM, Akande S. Men's Awareness, Support and Uptake of Modern Family Planning: A Case Study of Oyo State Nigeria. *Texila Int J Public Health*. 2024 Sep 1;12(3).
5. Assaf S, Davis LM. Women's modern contraceptive use in sub-Saharan Africa: does men's involvement matter? *J Glob Health Rep*. 2019 Mar 15;3.
6. Michael TO, Ekpenyong AS. The Polygyny-Fertility Hypothesis: New Evidences from Nigeria. *Niger J Sociol Anthropol*. 2018 Jun 1;16(1):167–181.
7. Chae S, Agadjanian V. The Transformation of Polygyny in Sub-Saharan Africa. *Popul Dev Rev*. 2022 Dec 1;48(4):1125–62.
8. Bongaarts J. Trends in fertility and fertility preferences in sub-Saharan Africa: the roles of education and family planning programs. *Genus*. 2020 Dec 21;76(1):32.
9. Osborne A, Ahinkorah BO. The paternal influence on early childhood development in Africa: implications for child and adolescent mental health. *Child Adolesc Psychiatry Ment Health*. 2024 Dec 6;18(1):156.
10. Repetti RL, Taylor SE, Seeman TE. Risky families: Family social environments and the mental and physical health of offspring. *Psychol Bull*. 2002 Mar;128(2):330–366.
11. Engdawork K, D'Ambruso L, Hailu T, Yared M, Geletu GM, Baraki SG, et al. "Space to see the future"? A political economy analysis of child and adolescent mental health and well-being in Ethiopia including routes for change. *Fron Soc*. 2025 Feb 6;9.
12. Van den Berg W, Ratele K, Malinga M, Makusha T. State of South Africa's Fathers 2024 [Internet]. Stellenbosch; 2024. www.equimundo.org/resources/state-of-the-worlds-fathers-2023/. Accessed on 10 January 2026.
13. Aboagye RG, Essuman MA, Dzirasah KD, Seidu AA, Adnani QES, Ahinkorah BO. Association between polygyny and justification of violence among women in sexual unions in sub-Saharan Africa. *BMC Public Health*. 2025 Dec 1;25(1).
14. Michael TO, Naidoo K. The influence of wife abuse on women's reproductive choices in Southern African Countries: Findings from a cross-sectional analysis of demographic and health surveys. *Afr J Reprod Health*. 2024 Oct 31;28(10):99–111.
15. Nhampoca JM, Maritz JE. Early marriage, education and mental health: experiences of adolescent girls in Mozambique. *Front Glob Womens Health*. 2024 Jun 12;5.
16. Ainamani HE, Mbwayo AW, Mathai M, Karlsson L, Zari Rukundo G. Post-traumatic stress disorder and its associated factors: a cross-sectional study among refugee children and adolescents living in a Ugandan refugee settlement. *Eur J Psychotraumatol*. 2025 Dec 31;16(1).
17. Naidoo Y, Joubert L, Nhakaniso K, Nzeribe E, Akinsolu FT, Okova D, et al. Socioeconomic determinants of male contraceptive use in South Africa: a secondary analysis of the 2016 SADHS data. *BMC Public Health*. 2024 Dec 1;24(1):2756.
18. Lokko C, Sackey J, Lokko F. Factors influencing type of contraceptive use among Ghanaian males: Insights from the 2022 Ghana demographic and health survey. *Public Health Pract*. 2025 Jun;9:100623.
19. Okunlola DA, Ilesanmi BB, Kierian EU, Awoleye AF. Exposure to Family Planning Messages, Feminization of Contraception, and Tendency to Stigmatize Female Contraceptive Users Among Partnered Men in Northern Nigeria. *J Mens Stud*. 2025 Jun 11;33(2):372–393.

20. Mebrahtu H, Chimbindi N, Zuma T, Dreyer J, Mthiyane N, Seeley J, et al. Incident pregnancy and mental health among adolescent girls and young women in rural KwaZulu-Natal, South Africa: an observational cohort study. *Int J Adolesc Youth*. 2024 Dec 31;29(1).
21. Kwesiga JM, Namuli JD, Akimana B, Serunjogi JN, Kitaka SB, Seggane M, et al. Prevalence and factors associated with mental health challenges among adolescents with HIV and viral non-suppression in rural northern Uganda. *Front Public Health*. 2025 Jun 20;13.
22. World Bank. Fertility rate, total (births per woman) | Data - South Africa [Internet]. 2023 <https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SP.DYN.TFRT.IN>. Accessed on 30 April 2025.
23. Biney E, Amoateng A, Ewemooje O. Patterns of fertility in contemporary South Africa: Prevalence and associated factors. *Cogent Soc Sci*. 2021;7(1).
24. Republic of South Africa. Marriages and divorces 2023 [Internet]. Pretoria; 2025 Mar. www.statssa.gov.za.info@statssa.gov.za,Tel+27123108911. Accessed on 10 January 2026.
25. Baird S, Choonara S, Azzopardi PS, Banati P, Bessant J, Biermann O, et al. A call to action: the second Lancet Commission on adolescent health and wellbeing. *The Lancet*. 2025 May;405(10493):1945–2022.
26. Amouzou A, Barros AJD, Requejo J, Faye C, Akseer N, Bendavid E, et al. The 2025 report of the Lancet Countdown to 2030 for women's, children's, and adolescents' health: tracking progress on health and nutrition. *Lancet*. 2025 Apr;405(10488):1505–1554.
27. World Health Organization. Family planning/contraception methods [Internet]. WHO. 2025 <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/family-planning-contraception>. Accessed on 1 August 2025.
28. Boyle EH, King M, Sobek M. IPUMS-Demographic and Health Surveys: Version 9 [dataset]. IPUMS and ICF. 2022.
29. Vandembroucke JP, von Elm E, Altman DG, Gøtzsche PC, Mulrow CD, Pocock SJ, et al. Strengthening the Reporting of Observational Studies in Epidemiology (STROBE): explanation and elaboration. *Int J Surg [Internet]*. 2014;12(12):1500–1524.
30. Demissie KA, Jejaw M, Teshale G, Tiruneh MG, Tafere TZ, Hagos A. Multinomial multilevel analysis of factors affecting the use of modern contraceptives in sub-Saharan Africa: evidence from 2015 to 2023 Demographic Health Survey. *Sci Rep*. 2025 May 14;15(1):16751.
31. Abbani AY. Factors Associated with Men's Fertility Intentions and Family Planning Practice in Kebbi State, North-western Nigeria. *Ife Soc Sci Rev [Internet]*. 2023;31(1):67–82.
32. Kizza J, Wasswa G. Education and Fertility preference among women in Uganda. *Tanzan J Health Res*. 2024 Jun 26;25(3):989–1002.
33. Nkuye M, Tina NM, Xiaochun Q, Jilei W, Xiaoying Z. Measuring Independent and Controlled Effects of Age at First Marriage and Age at First Birth on Completed Family Size among Women Aged 45-49 in Zambia. *Int J Womens Health Wellness*. 2022 Feb 9;8(1).
34. Buyinza F, Hisali E. Microeffects of Women's Education on Contraceptive Use and Fertility: The Case of Uganda. *J Int Dev*. 2014 Aug 8;26(6):763–778.
35. Dwomoh D, Amuasi S, Amoah E, Gborgbortsi W, Tetteh J. Exposure to family planning messages and contraceptive use among women of reproductive age in sub-Saharan Africa: a cross-sectional program impact. *Sci Rep [Internet]*. 2022;12(1):18941.
36. Agbana RD, Michael TO, Ojo TF. Family planning method discontinuation among Nigerian women: Evidence from the Nigeria Demographic and Health Survey 2018. *J Taibah Univ Med Sci*. 2023 Feb 1;18(1):117–124.
37. Stevens SM, Faiaz MM, Rao N, Raj A. Ugandans applaud government efforts to promote gender equality, but want more [Internet]. 2023 Jan. <https://www.afrobarometer.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/01/AD588-Ugandans-applaud-government-efforts-to-promote-gender-equality-but-want-more-Afrobarometer-9jan23.pdf>. Accessed on 29 February 2024.
38. Mokitimi S, Jonas K, Schneider M, de Vries PJ. Where is Batho Pele? The perspective of child and adolescent mental health service users in the Western Cape Province of South Africa. *BMC Public Health*. 2025 Jan 24;25(1):305.
39. Shumet T, Geda NR. Impacts of inequalities in utilization of key maternal health service on fertility preference among high parity women in four selected regions of Ethiopia. *BMC Womens Health*. 2024 Nov 5;24(1):590.

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